

The expertise centre Diamond Open Access operates under below values:

- **Openness:** we believe that access to scholarly work needs to be freely accessible to everyone without charging fees to authors and readers in order to ensure equity and inclusivity of access and distribution of knowledge. We adhere to this principle by operating openly and transparently, for example, by sharing all the resources we create under a CC-BY license.
- **Quality:** we uphold the highest quality standards of the information and services provided. We are committed to promoting international quality standards for Institutional Publishers and editors by following closely the best practices set up by [OASPA](#), and the quality standards developed within the [DIAMAS](#) project. In this way, we also commit ourselves to promoting international quality standards for institutional publishers and editors.
- **Sustainability:** we advocate that Diamond Open Access needs to be a financially sustainable open access model before it can be scalable.
- **Service- and community-oriented:** we set our agenda and priorities with feedback from the community, and we pivot when we need to. We put our partners and members at the core of what we do.
- **Collaboration:** we believe that collaborating with libraries, publishers, editors, researchers, policy, and funders is indispensable for the consolidation and sustainability of Diamond Open Access. We will be actively seeking to collaborate with relevant parties.
- **Inclusivity and diversity:** we advocate for an inclusive and diverse open access scholarly publishing model in which Diamond Open Access publishers thrive.

This is the version appeared on our website in 2025, they have been removed from the website to increase its readability.